

THE BLUE FOUR'S INCORPOREAL VOYAGE TO AMERICA

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SUMMARY

While multiple parallels can be drawn between The Blue Rider (1911–1914) and The Blue Four (1924–1940), the geographical connections pursued by the two artist groups notably diverge. The former looked up to the East, particularly Russia, as the locus of the forthcoming »spiritual revolution«; the latter turned their attention toward and tried to establish their ideas in the New World. The Blue Four's promotional activities in America during the interwar period can

be explained as a pursuit of profits in the country that was wealthier and economically more stable than the emaciated by the war Europe. On the other hand, the interest in the United States can suggest a continuation of The Blue Rider's hopeful search for the center of spiritual awakening. The present essay introduces the connections between the two »blue« circles and inquires why The Blue Four send their art and ideas on a westward mission.

Fig. 1
Wassily Kandinsky, final design for the cover of The Blue Rider Almanac, 1911, watercolor, ink and pencil on paper, 27.9 cm x 21.9 cm, Städtische Galerie im Lenbachhaus und Kunstbau München, Gabriele Münter Stiftung 1957
© Städtische Galerie im Lenbachhaus und Kunstbau

»» BECAUSE BLUE IS A SPIRITUAL COLOR««

The Blue Rider was not an official association but rather a circle of friends and like-minded artists who gathered in Munich around Wassily Kandinsky and Franz Marc. Between 1911 and 1914 they organized two exhibitions and published one issue of The Blue Rider Almanac (FIG. 1). First World War put an end to the group's activities, taking the lives of Marc as well as »blue riders« Wladimir Burljuk and August Macke. The war also forced the Russian members of the group—Jawlensky, Kandinsky, and Marianne von Werefkin—to flee from Germany.

After the war, Walter Gropius appointed three artists formerly associated with The Blue Rider to teach at the newly founded State Bauhaus in Weimar: Lyonel Feininger (1871–1956), Paul Klee (1879–1940) and Kandinsky (1866–1944).

Likewise invited, Jawlensky (1864–1941) turned down the director's offer on the premise that art could not be taught and instead settled in Wiesbaden.¹ In early 1924, at the initiative of Jawlensky's long-time friend, art devotee and painter Emilie Scheyer (1889–1945), they joined together

Fig. 2
The Blue Four, cover of the exhibition
catalog, The Oakland Art Gallery, 1931
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under the name The Blue Four (FIG. 2).² Feininger's suggestion »The 4« was nearly accepted but needed to be changed because a group of Danish painters had already exhibited under the same name.³ Whereas the addition of an adjective appears pragmatic at first, it responds to the artists' wish that the name ought to »suggest nothing less than the founding character, the spiritual leadership, or, that which is the most beautiful about it, the friendship«. The added descriptor unmistakably refers to The Blue Rider, as confirmed by Scheyer in writing: »The color blue comes from the earlier group in Munich which founded the 'Blue Rider' ... and also because blue is a spiritual color«. ⁵

Fig. 3
Alexej Jawlensky, *Sad Galka, Singing Galka, Resting Galka*, 1921–1922, pencil on wove paper, 19.4 x 39.1 cm, Norton Simon Museum, The Blue Four Galka Scheyer Collection
© Norton Simon Museum

Such reference allows for parallels between »the founding character« and »the spiritual leadership« of the two groups.⁶ For the pre-war circle these meant the virtue and significance of the artist's inner life and inner need to create; liberation of art from outer life, i. e. from the question of form; artist's responsibility to fuel the »spiritual revolution« by enriching the viewer's soul and to cure the contemporary society of »extreme materialism« and commercialism of the day.⁷ Such principles defined the mission and activities of The Blue Rider and, even as the group dissolved with the outbreak of the First World War, they lived on in the work of individual artists. It was exactly these ideals that united the five friends in 1924.

»A MISSION HERE ON EARTH«

Encounter with Alexej von Jawlensky's art changed the life of Emilie Scheyer, who adopted the name »Galka« (FIG. 3) after his dream and set aside her own painting in order to promote Jawlensky's work.⁸ In 1923 she received, as if »dropping from the stars«, an invitation letter sent by the artist Rajah von Rubio from Ossining, New York.⁹ In addition to Jawlensky's paintings Scheyer originally planned to bring and exhibit in America works by such artists as Oskar Kokoschka, Emil Nolde, El Lissitzky, László Moholy-Nagy, and Kurt Schwitters.¹⁰ The fact that it was Feininger, Jawlensky, Kandinsky, and Klee who eventually formed a group attests to the continuity of the blue riders' lofty ideals. On 31 March 1924 the artists signed the founding contract of the »free group of the blue four« and outlined their purpose as »dissemination of their artistic ideas abroad, especially through lectures and exhibitions«. ¹¹ To that end Scheyer received artworks on commission but no remuneration for either her work or travel expenses, apart from thirty percent of proceeds in case of a sale.¹² Antithetical to customary profit-oriented partnerships between artists and dealers,

Fig. 4

Lyonel Feininger, *Peaceful Voyage III*, 1933, watercolor and India ink on laid paper, 27.3 x 28.6 cm, Norton Simon Museum, The Blue Four Galka Scheyer Collection. Inscribed along the lower edge: »To his Little Friend Galka Emmy, from Papileo, zur Erinnerung an die Zeit, Juni, 1936«
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The Blue Four's contract laid the primary emphasis on education and communication. What is more, they did not expect Scheyer's trip to be profitable. Feininger (**FIG. 4**) cautioned her: »I admit, I see no particular chances for success in the United States, here I have much higher prices and one scrambles to get my works [...] Klee (**FIG. 5**) is of the same opinion—the dollar has played its role in Germany out, and makes for only 4.20 Marks, as erst-while. Also in Switzerland, Holland, and elsewhere abroad, art has no more power. Only in Germany it is a truly inner necessity«. ¹³ Along similar lines he later related Georg Muche's trip to America: »He was in New York for barely two weeks and instead of going on as planned to Los Angeles, he decided suddenly to return to Germany be-

Fig. 5

Paul Klee, *The Saint*, 1921, watercolor and oil transfer drawing on laid paper, mounted on thin cardboard, 45.1 x 31.1 cm, Norton Simon Museum, The Blue Four Galka Scheyer Collection. Inscribed on the mount, lower right: »Für Emy Scheyer in Freundschaft Weihnachten 1921 Kl.«
© Norton Simon Museum

cause he realized that there is simply no room in America for our European art and affairs. [...] So, don't expect our European art to immediately win everyone over, or even interest them«. ¹⁴ Again in December Feininger reiterated his skepticism: »Why should I attempt to sell my pictures elsewhere, and then, for the circumstances there, at ridiculously low prices? Here [in Germany] my work is understood and is ardently sought after. There [in America], my works are more likely to be bought as a 'curiosity'«. ¹⁵ It did not help Scheyer that the American audience remained largely conservative in its views on art and that connections with Germany as the aggressor in the First World War were additionally unwelcome. ¹⁶ A case in point is the exhibition *Modern German Art* that took place at The Anderson Galleries in New York in October 1923 and was described by one American newspaper as a »dismal failure«. ¹⁷ Concurrently, a patriotic attitude was gaining ground in the cultural sphere: »The time has arrived when the American Artist is the equal, if not superior, of the foreign artist. [...] America is marching on to an artistic renaissance which will carry the nation to a great cultured height«. ¹⁸ Thus, the prospect of financial success for the group that included one German and two Russians could not be positive. In spite of that the blue fours, or rather fives, expressed distinct enthusiasm about making connections with the New World. ¹⁹ The question arises as to why.

Writing to her family a few months after arriving to America, Scheyer (**FIG. 6**) explained that monetary profit was not the goal of her trip: »I have been given a mission here on earth and I know that those chosen by God must suffer, for one can only truly give of oneself when by suffering one has acquired insight and achieved inner growth. I do know that I would not trade my life with anyone else and I believe that the founding of 'The Blue Four' and the trust of these artists is reward enough, in order to

Fig. 6
Emmy Galka Scheyer, 1920, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, gift from the Klee family, photo: anonymous
© Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, image archive

Fig. 7
Alexej Jawlensky, letter to Galka Scheyer and Hunchback, 1928, watercolor and ink on grey wove paper, 21.0 x 16.5 cm, Norton Simon Museum, The Blue Four Galka Scheyer Collection
© Norton Simon Museum

be satisfied with my fate. That is not a success that can be measured by coins on the table, but a success that even in my boldest dreams I could not have imagined at the beginning of my path.²⁰ The letter reveals Scheyer's religious understanding of life

and of her vocation,²¹ which was shared by and united the four artists. An orthodox Christian, Jawlensky (**FIG. 7**) openly spoke about his art in relation to faith: »[...] the artist must express through his art, in form and color, the divine inside him. That is why a work of art is God made visible, and art is 'a longing for God'«. ²² Kandinsky (**FIG. 8**), who likewise adhered to Orthodox Christianity throughout his life, believed that artistic talent was a divine gift from God as well as a calling to be »the servant of higher ends, whose duty is precise and holy«. ²³ Less religiously, Klee's wrote about the »divine self« of an artist,²⁴ while Feininger saw the process of artistic creation as the meaning and »law of life«. ²⁵ The artists' experience of connection with divine calling and earnest devotion to their work went hand in hand with their belief in the spiritual significance of modern art. That belief is exemplified in one of Scheyer's last letters to Jawlensky: »[Your] Variations were the first things that I understood of art and they reveal to me again and again the secret of life. [...] I thought that when people again begin to look into their souls, your work would be prophetic for them«. ²⁶ The shared conviction that art »awakens and moves the human soul« ²⁷ was the cornerstone of the artists' alliance. In Scheyer's own words, »the Blue Four was founded in order to share with Amer-

Fig. 8
Wassily Kandinsky, *The Small Blue*, July 1924, watercolor on paper, 48.6 x 33.6 cm, private collection
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ica the spirit embodied in these [art] works and to get away from art dealers«. ²⁸ The paramount mission was therefore not to conquer a new market but rather »to carry on the spiritual in the world«, ²⁹ that is, to continue where The Blue Rider left off.

» YOUNG PEOPLE ... ONLY THEY ARE THE FUTURE«

Consistent with the mission was the group's emphasis on education: »dissemination of their artistic ideas abroad, especially through lectures and exhibitions«. After the plan to speak at Smith College in summer 1924 fell through, Galka Scheyer conceived a lecture tour across the United States and launched a tremendous mailing campaign with over 600 letters to universities and colleges and 400 pamphlets to museums and cultural institutions. »God willing, this will result in a lecture tour, which will give me the opportunity to plant in a few young souls the seeds lying dormant in the art of the Blue Four and waiting only for their reception«. ³⁰ The intended audience was thus American youth: »I am not expecting any sales [...]. There is only one field to be ploughed here and that is with the educational institutions and the youth. America is young and loves to learn«. ³¹ It is relevant that throughout her life Scheyer was giving art lessons to

children; she actively promoted art pedagogy and occasionally organized exhibitions of her pupils' works. ³² The other blue fours, as well as the blue riders earlier, shared the same belief that art was conducive to spiritual growth and that by means of art they could plant the seeds for the »Great Spiritual« future. ³³ As the public reception of The Blue Rider's exhibitions and almanac remained largely negative, Kandinsky and Marc concluded that »the time was not ripe for 'hearing' and 'seeing'« but expressed »justified hope« that the ripeness was oncoming. ³⁴ They were prepared to wait for it, even if that meant waiting for the next generation and not witnessing the new spiritual epoch firsthand. The artists anticipated spiritual awakening to arise from the East, particularly from Russia—the view that gave way following the October Revolution, the restricted artistic freedom under the Bolshevik regime, and Kandinsky's relocation from Moscow to Germany. ³⁵ For a short while, the Bauhaus was promising to become the locus of the spiritual movement. Feininger's woodcut of a Christian cathedral for the cover of the school's manifesto was not an arbitrary choice. Gropius' aspiration to build »a world of beauty built completely anew«, ³⁶ together with an opportunity to teach the young generation of artists and craftsmen, must have appealed to Feininger, Kandinsky and Klee (FIG. 9). From 1923 the school's founding principles gradually yielded to the sway of New Objectivity, which set to replace lofty idealism and romanticism with a techno-scientific practicality. The appointment of László Moholy-Nagy to the teaching position previously occupied by Johannes Itten signaled the change within Bauhaus. Instead of seeing art as the inner workings of human spirit, the former advocated functionalism and rationalistic approach to art production: »You surely don't believe the old fairy-tale about the human soul«. ³⁷ The new orientation toward the mass production of inexpensive products could not be embraced by the

Fig. 9
Paul Klee and Wassily Kandinsky drinking tea in front of their Masters' House at Bauhaus Dessau, 1929/1930, photo: likely Nina Kandinsky, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, gift from the Klee family
© Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, image archive

Fig. 10
The Bauhaus masters on the roof of the Bauhaus building in Dessau, December 1926.
From the left: Josef Albers, Hinnerk Scheper, Georg Muche, László Moholy-Nagy, Herbert Bayer, Joost Schmidt, Walter Gropius, Marcel Breuer, Wassily Kandinsky, Paul Klee, Lyonel Feininger, Gunta Stölzl and Oskar Schlemmer.
Photo: anonymous
Bauhaus-Archiv Berlin / Musée National d'Art Moderne / Centre de Création Industrielle, Centre Georges Pompidou, Paris, legs Nina Kandinsky

former blue riders: »The machine's way of functioning is not bad, but life is something more. Life engenders and bears.«³⁸ As the belief in the spiritual origin of art became amiss, the artistic positions of The Blue Four (**FIG. 10**) were now regarded as conservative and were even subject to the derision of some students and colleagues.³⁹ Kandinsky described the change in public sensibility: »The 'new objectivity' has become the fashion—a surface realism, propped up by the old German masters. The 'national thought'! It's a superficialization, which a couple years ago would have been unimaginable. [...] Perhaps in the end the Americans will show themselves to be the smarter ones after all [sic], even if one first has to wait for the next generation.«⁴⁰ With New Objectivity gaining ground in Germany, the initial enthusiasm about the Bauhaus as the locus of the spiritual movement all but vanished and The Blue Four joined together in order to disseminate their artistic ideas in »the new land«. It was arguably the youthful character of the United States as a country—the »Ameri-Young«⁴¹—that motivated them to send their artworks and ideas on a transatlantic mission.

»FAITH IN THE IDEA«

It would be remiss to say Galka Scheyer was not interested in selling works by her friends in America. Although she »could not imagine a more psychologically unpleasant profession than dealing in art«,⁴² sales were a necessity, especially for Jawlensky, who did not hold a teaching position, and for all the group members after 1933. Yet the primary purpose of Scheyer's work on behalf of The Blue Four was otherwise: »For the past 12 years, I have worked in America for the sake of art. And also for the money it brings? As anyone can see, money plays no role, but the love of art does. [...] Exactly because of and despite the lack of material success, the more avid this faith in the idea. [...] what matters to me? Kindling a small flicker of light in one soul or another. So I do my best, which is most sacred to me.«⁴³ Just as the above cited family letter, Scheyer's intimate correspondence with the blue fours reveals her religiosity as well as her belief in art as the »divine language of men«. In one especially heartfelt letter to Feininger (**FIG. 11**) she exalted his paintings: »The voice of your most marvelous works is devout and pious—it rings out of crystal heights, [...] resonates with the voices of the inner forces to reach oneness, which prays faithfully,—rests divinely in its being.«⁴⁴ In response to such letters Darcy Tell astutely observes: »Scheyer's vocation for modern art—and I mean vocation in the religious sense—is something foreign and perplexing to us now, as it certainly was to most Americans in her day. Steeped as we are in postmodern irony, high-flown discussions of artistic idealism now understandably appear to us naïve or embarrassingly earnest.«⁴⁵ In spite of the seeming naïveté, it is necessarily the blue fours' certitude regarding their vocation and their faith in the divine essence of artistic talent that helps us to understand what brought them together and drove them—albeit for three-fifths of the group incorporeally—to the

Fig. 11
Lyonel Feininger, letter to Galka Scheyer, 1932 and *Buildings with Crescent Moon*, 1920, woodcut on blue wove tissue paper, 28.3 x 21.9 cm, Norton Simon Museum, The Blue Four Galka Scheyer Collection
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»new land«. Formerly the mission of The Blue Rider, between 1924 and 1940 it was the purpose of The Blue Four to enrich the viewer's soul through their art and thus to carry on the spiritual in the world. The artists' faith in the spiritual awakening among the young American audience was a necessity because to them art could not exist in a totally secular world, similar to the one that was encroaching upon them in the socio-political climate of the interwar Europe.

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¹ Weiler 1959, p. 108.

² For a detailed account of the founding of The Blue Four, see Wünsche 2006, pp. 29-34.

³ Barnett/Helfenstein 1997, p. 19.

⁴ Wünsche 2006, p. 38.

⁵ Ibid., p. 31 (quoted from *Paul Klee Memorial Exhibition: Addenda to the Exhibition of The Museum of Modern Art*, San Francisco: San Francisco Museum of Art, 1941, p. 5). Cf. Scheyer's introduction to the unpublished manuscript »America's Youth and Modern Art«: »These four friends chose, specifically for this event, to call themselves 'The Blue Four,' after the 'Blaue Reiter' (founded by Kandinsky and Marc in 1912).« Ibid., p. 347.

⁶ It should be noted that all four artists of The Blue Four were earlier associated with The Blue Rider. In addition to the founder Kandinsky, Jawlensky and Klee participated in the group's exhibitions and remained in close contact with one another. Feininger was introduced to the group by Alfred Kubin in 1913 and, in spite of the former's reluctance to join any faction or party, the artist developed affinity towards the blue riders' pursuit of individual and »innermost expression« in art. Hünecke 1991, pp. 470, 484-485, and 531.

⁷ Kandinsky/Marc 1912, p. 38.

⁸ Angelica Jawlensky, » 'Ich habe meine Kunst in Ihre Hände gelegt' : Emmy Scheyer und Alexej von Jawlensky—eine Freundschaft, « in Barnett/Helfenstein 1997, pp. 63-78. For an account of the dream with a jackdaw, see pages 65-66.

⁹ Ibid., p. 75.

¹⁰ Barnett 2002, p. 13.

¹¹ The contract in German is reproduced in Barnett/Helfenstein 1997, pp. 292-293.

¹² Fifty percent went to the artist and the remaining twenty to the joint account of the group.

¹³ Feininger to Scheyer, 24 February 1924, in Barnett/Helfenstein 1997, p. 18. The notion »inner necessity« makes an additional and particularly strong connection between The Blue Rider and The Blue Four. Cf. Friedel/Hoberg 2013, p. 21; Hünecke 1991, p. 529; Wünsche 2006, pp. 13, 98, 257, 344, 346.

- 14 Feininger to Scheyer, 3 May 1924, in Wünsche 2006, p. 52. Cf. Kandinsky to Scheyer, 2 May 1924, *ibid.*, p. 51.
- 15 *Ibid.*, p. 84.
- 16 Kentgens-Craig 1999, p. 58.
- 17 Feininger to Scheyer, 13 December 1924, in Wünsche 2006, p. 82.
- 18 Statement of the League of American Artists, New York, 1923, quoted in Kentgens-Craig 1999, p. 18.
- 19 Cf. Wünsche 2006, pp. 34, 36, 51, 53, and 72.
- 20 *Ibid.*, p. 62. In the letter Scheyer rejected her brothers' offer of permanent financial support, which they made on the condition that she returned to Germany.
- 21 The religious undertone of such notions as vocation and calling, or »a sacred duty«, can often be found in Scheyer's writings. Cf. *ibid.*, pp. 29, 41, 74, 166, 258, 344-345. Isabel Wünsche also describes Scheyer as »a prophet«, »a missionary and pioneer in the field of modern art« and explains her zeal with »deep love for life, her untiring enthusiasm, and her almost religious understanding of art« (*ibid.*, pp. 12-13, 20). Given Scheyer's frequent references to God especially in the letters to Jawlensky, it is illuminating to speak of her forthright religious view on art.
- 22 Jawlensky 1938, p. 268.
- 23 Kandinsky/Lindsay/Vergo 1994, p. 370. Cf. Sokolova 2018, pp. 146-147.
- 24 Tower 1981, p. 123 and Hünecke 1991, pp. 537-538.
- 25 Barnett/Helfenstein 1997, pp. 133-134.
- 26 Scheyer to Jawlensky, 6 April 1940, in Wünsche 2006, p. 291.
- 27 Scheyer to Jawlensky, 8 January 1941, in *ibid.*, p. 295.
- 28 Scheyer's collective letter to the four artists, 10 March 1936, in *ibid.*, p. 257.
- 29 Scheyer to Kandinsky, 5 September 1938, in *ibid.*, p. 8.
- 30 *Ibid.*, pp. 9 and 60.
- 31 Scheyer's collective letter, 1/9 June 1926, in *ibid.*, p. 137.
- 32 Galka E. Scheyer, Address to the International Congress for Art Education in Prague, August 1928, in *ibid.*, pp. 352-355. Comparably, The Blue Rider almanac included pictures made by children.
- 33 *Ibid.*, pp. 68, 74, 121, 161, 298, 347-351.
- 34 Preface to the second edition of the almanac, 1914, in Hünecke 1991, p. 160.
- 35 Kandinsky/Lindsay/Vergo 1994, p. 896. The full passage reads: »It is through the gradual freeing of the spirit—the major blessing of our age—that there become ever more evident in many quarters an interest and a growing faith in the future of Russia and in Russia itself«.
- 36 Whitford 1984, p. 40.
- 37 Moholy-Nagy's letter to Lothar Schreyer, quoted in *ibid.*, p. 127.
- 38 Klee quoted in *ibid.*, p. 132.
- 39 Barnett/Helfenstein 1997, pp. 121-122. Their separateness within the school is evident in Oskar Schlemmer's description: »These families [Kandinsky, Klee, Feininger] have a kind of calm inner richness from which they live. We are nervous wretches. Perhaps we'll get there yet as well«. (*Ibid.*, p. 123). In Feininger's own words, the Klees, the Kandinskys and the Feiningers »will stick together bravely«. (*Ibid.*, p. 292).
- 40 Kandinsky to Scheyer, 6 October 1925, in Wünsche 2006, p. 119.
- 41 Quotes from Kandinsky's letters, Wünsche 2006, pp. 51 and 214. In her first year in America Scheyer wrote of »the youthful rhythm of this country«; *ibid.*, p. 79.
- 42 *Ibid.*, p. 42.
- 43 Scheyer's collective letter, 10 March 1936, in *ibid.*, pp. 255-258. Cf. p. 125: »in order to advance the idea (which is holy to me)...« and p. 170: »my person is not important; right it is a question of the greater plan«.
- 44 Barnett/Helfenstein 1997, p. 292.
- 45 Tell 2010.

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